

Multiple Testing in Remote Sensing: Addressing the Elephant in the Room

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Highlights:

- After searching 20 yr. of remote sensing literature, few addressed multiple testing.
- False discovery rate (FDR) control is rarely applied in remote sensing.
- Spurious findings from uncontrolled FDR can lead to misleading conclusions.
- FDR can be easily controlled to a pre-specified level.

18 **Abstract:**

19 In environmental remote sensing, statistical tests are often conducted at the pixel level,
20 generating thousands of p -values and substantially increasing the risk of Type I errors.
21 Traditional multiple testing corrections aim to control the probability of any false
22 positives, but often at the cost of drastically reduced statistical power. In contrast, false
23 discovery rate (FDR) control limits the proportion of false positives among significant
24 results while preserving power. It is widely used in image-based disciplines such as
25 neuroimaging and, more broadly, medical imaging, where error control is critical.
26 However, its adoption in remote sensing remains unclear. We conducted a Scopus-based
27 review of twenty years of literature (2004–2023) in remote sensing journals to assess the
28 use of FDR control in spatiotemporal trend analyses, with particular attention to studies
29 employing the Mann-Kendall test, a non-parametric method widely used for detecting
30 monotonic trends at the pixel level. Our results reveal that only 0.03% of remote sensing
31 articles cited the seminal Benjamini–Hochberg (1995) method, and none of the studies
32 using pixel-wise Mann-Kendall testing explicitly applied FDR control. This striking
33 absence highlights a critical risk of overestimating significance in large-scale remote
34 sensing analyses, especially as increasing data precision demands more rigorous error
35 control. We call for routinely incorporating FDR procedures into remote sensing
36 workflows to control the inflation of Type I error in large-scale multiple testing.

37 **Keywords:** multiple hypothesis testing, multiplicity, gridded data, spatiotemporal trends,
38 statistical significance, p -values, false discovery rate (FDR); environmental remote
39 sensing.

40

41 **1. Introduction.**

42 In environmental remote sensing, statistical tests are conducted independently for each
43 pixel within gridded datasets, generating large numbers of p -values and leading to
44 multiple simultaneous inferences —a challenge known as the multiple testing problem
45 (Cortés et al., 2020).

46 Multiple testing and large-scale inference are well-established statistics topics (Efron,
47 2010). Among the various approaches to multiple testing correction, the false discovery
48 rate (FDR) is a more effective and flexible alternative (Miller et al., 2001). Traditional
49 multiple testing corrections, such as the Bonferroni method, control the family-wise error
50 rate (FWER) —the probability of making at least one false positive—, but at the cost of
51 drastically reducing statistical power (García, 2004). In contrast, FDR controls the
52 proportion of false positives among statistically significant results, preserving statistical
53 power (Benjamini, 2010). This balance between sensitivity and reliability makes FDR
54 particularly important for correcting p -values in digital significance maps (Genovese et
55 al., 2002), where large-scale per-pixel analyses generate thousands of statistical tests. The
56 false discovery rate (FDR) was defined by Benjamini & Hochberg (1995) as the expected
57 proportion of false discoveries among all discoveries:

58
$$\text{FDR} = E \left[\frac{V}{R} \right] \quad [1]$$

59 Where:

60 E denotes the expected value

61 V is the number of false positives (false discoveries).

62 R is the total number of rejected hypotheses (discoveries).

63 The original FDR approach, known as the Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure
64 (described in detail, with graphical support, in *Supplemental Material I*), uses a linear
65 step-up method that allows for setting an upper limit to the expected proportion of false
66 positives (q)¹, frequently 5%, within the subset of p -values that were found to be
67 statistically significant (i.e., those tests having p -values $< \alpha$), after performing multiple
68 (m) hypothesis tests at the pixel-scale. That is, the BH procedure guarantees that:

69
$$\text{FDR} = E \left[\frac{V}{R} \right] \leq q \quad [2]$$

70 The BH procedure involves calculating a new rejection threshold (α^*) for individual tests
71 and rejecting H_0 for all tests with a p -value $\leq \alpha^*$. Alternatively, a set of adjusted p -values
72 (adj. p -values) can be calculated, rejecting the null hypothesis for all those tests with an
73 adj. p -value $\leq q$. Box 1 outlines the FDR control's key features and comparative
74 advantages (Miller et al., 2001).

75 [Box 1. Place Box 1 here.](#)

76 The BH procedure assumes all tested hypotheses correspond to true nulls, guaranteeing
77 FDR control under independence and positive dependence (Benjamini and Yekutieli,
78 2001). However, in many practical applications—including remote sensing—this
79 assumption can be considered overly stringent, as a substantial proportion of the tests

¹ While α (alpha) is typically used to control the Family-Wise Error Rate (FWER) in traditional multiple testing corrections—i.e., the probability of making at least one Type I error across all tests—, q denotes the maximum acceptable proportion of Type I errors among all rejected hypotheses under false discovery rate (FDR) procedures. In practice, both thresholds are often set to 0.05; however, q controls the expected rate of false discoveries among findings, rather than the probability of a single false positive. Setting $\alpha = 0.05$ implies a 5% chance of obtaining at least one false positive across all tests, whereas setting $q = 0.05$ means that, on average, only 5% of the rejected hypotheses are expected to be false discoveries.

80 assumed to reflect null hypotheses may, in fact, correspond to genuine effects. To
81 improve statistical power in such settings, Benjamini, Krieger & Yekutieli (2006)
82 proposed an adaptive step-up procedure that estimates the number of true null hypotheses
83 (m_0) and adjusts the rejection threshold accordingly. This approach enhances sensitivity
84 while maintaining valid FDR control at the pre-specified level q , ensuring the expected
85 proportion of false discoveries among all rejections does not exceed the chosen threshold
86 (see *Supplemental Material I* for details).

87 Multiple testing was identified as a concern in environmental remote sensing research
88 several years ago (Clements et al., 2014a; Heumann, 2015). Similar challenges have long
89 been acknowledged in other remote sensing-based disciplines —most notably in
90 astrophysics, where the detection of celestial signals relies on analogous pixel-wise
91 inference procedures (Miller et al., 2001). However, its adoption remains unclear,
92 particularly in studies relying on extensive pixel-scale testing. In this cautionary note
93 presented as a short communication, we conduct a systematic review in the Scopus
94 database to quantify how much the false discovery rate (FDR) has been implemented in
95 remote sensing over 2004–2023.

96 Although the main objective of this short communication is to highlight the lack of FDR
97 implementation in remote sensing research, we also provide supplementary material to
98 assess its practical utility (see *Supplementary Material I & II*). Specifically, we include
99 an operational example and R code for applying FDR correction to raster-based gridded
100 datasets. Using a single raster layer of p -values as input, we illustrate two approaches: the
101 original Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995) and the
102 adaptive Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli (BKY) procedure (Benjamini et al., 2006).

103 2. Materials & Methods.

104 We conducted a systematic search for scientific publications in the *Scopus* database to
105 explore the citations received by the Benjamini & Hochberg (1995) seminal paper on
106 FDR (BH paper) in the Remote Sensing field. We chose this database due to its broader
107 coverage of journals and, especially, its capability of directly including search strings
108 from cited references within the initial document search. Since the Scopus database
109 organises its *Earth & Planetary Sciences* category into different subject areas, which do
110 not include a specific one for “Remote Sensing”, we decided to sample the field by
111 filtering for journal titles containing both the words “Remote” and “Sensing”. The Mann-
112 Kendall test was chosen because of its widespread use in detecting monotonic trends at
113 the pixel scale (McLeod, 2022)

114 Hence, we decided on a set of search criteria to find published articles focused on 1)
115 general papers published in the selected remote sensing journals, 2) papers focused on
116 trend tests applied to spatiotemporal gridded data in remote sensing, that cite the BH paper
117 over the last 20 years (2004-2023). For comparison, we selected articles from journals
118 focused on neuroimage analysis -those with “neuroimage” or “neuroimaging” in their
119 titles- and on a widely used medical imaging technique (fMRI, or functional magnetic
120 resonance imaging), as these are areas where the FDR method is likely to be most
121 frequently applied to control false positives in digital image analysis.

122 We defined a generic search string to gain a general impression of using false discovery
123 rate (FDR) control in the remote sensing research field and compare it with others. This
124 generic string was then modified by replacing search substrings in different search fields
125 to make the searches more specific. The generic search string used is detailed below:

126 SRCTITLE ([1]) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ([2]) AND DOCTYPE (ar) AND
127 PUBYEAR > 2003 AND PUBYEAR < 2024 AND [3]

128 where:

129 [1] is the journal TITLE search string

130 [2] is the article TITLE-ABSTRACT-KEYWORDS search string.

131 [3] is the cited reference search string, fixed as: REFPUYEAR = 1995 AND REFTITLE
132 (controlling) AND REFTITLE (false) AND REFTITLE (discovery) AND REFTITLE
133 (rate) AND REFAUTH (benjamini) AND REFAUTH (hochberg)

134 We used [1] = REMOTE SENSING to search articles published in journals mainly
135 dedicated to remote sensing. It involves twenty-six (26) journals listed in *Supplementary*
136 *Material III*.

137 We used [2] = AND trend AND analysis

138 [2] = [Spatio-temporal OR spatiotemporal] AND Trend AND Analysis

139 [2] = AND trend AND analysis AND [mann-kendall OR mann AND kendall)

140 to select articles referring to the selected topics in the different searches.

141

142 Furthermore, we used [1] = NEUROIMAG* to search for articles mainly dedicated to the
143 neuroimage/neuroimaging field; we found eight (8) indexed international journals listed
144 in *Supplementary Material III*. We also used [2] = fMRI, to select articles referring to
145 functional magnetic resonance.

146

147

148 **3. Results.**

149 Table 1 summarises the results of the searches performed in twenty-six (26) journals,
150 including “remote” and “sensing” in their title (see the complete journal list in
151 *Supplementary Material III*), in eight (8) neuroimage/neuroimaging journals and on
152 studies focused on fMRI (see *Supplementary Material III*).

153 Search strings used for searches and the lists of references resulting from applying them
154 to the selected remote sensing journals are included in *Supplementary Material III*.

155 [Table 1. Place Table 1 here.](#)

156 As seen in Table 1, the total number of articles published in the explored remote sensing
157 journals from the *Scopus* database was 89,802, with twenty-five (25) citations to BH
158 papers in the last 20 yr. The insights derived from these twenty-five search results focus
159 on statistical methods, including time series and trend analysis, machine learning and
160 neural networks. The most frequently used sensors are MODIS/Terra/Aqua (seven
161 articles), SAR (five articles), and AVHRR (three articles). Research topics predominantly
162 address vegetation (eleven articles), soil degradation (six articles), and climate analysis
163 (two articles). We also found that about half of citing papers were published in the last
164 three years (2021-2023). See *Supplementary Material III* for detailed results.

165 On the other hand, we found only two (2) references citing the BH paper on FDR among
166 829 research articles related explicitly to spatiotemporal trend analysis and five references
167 among 3,397 articles dealing with trend analysis in remote sensing in general. We found
168 no references that controlled for FDR among the 197 studies using specifically the pixel-
169 based Mann-Kendall test (Table 1).

170 Overall, the rate of use of the FDR control for multiple testing over the two-decade period
171 in the remote sensing journals examined was 0.03%, compared to 0.15, 0.24 and 0%,
172 respectively, for remote sensing studies performing any trend analysis, spatiotemporal
173 trend analysis and those specifically using the Mann-Kendall test (Table 1).

174 For illustrative purposes only, the lower panel of Table 1 presents the data from one of
175 the areas that most frequently applies this false positive control technique in digital image
176 analysis (Neuroimaging, fMRI). As expected, the FDR control is used more often (>200
177 times) than in the Remote Sensing journals examined.

178 **4. Discussion.**

179 Compared to other image-processing scientific fields, we found practically no apparent
180 usage or mention of the FDR control for multiple testing in the explored literature,
181 suggesting a significant gap. Over the period explored (2004-2023), we found only
182 twenty-five references to the seminal 1995 BH article among nearly 90,000 references
183 published in twenty-six remote sensing journals. Due to this low usage, much of the
184 widely used software for remote sensing data analysis still needs to include FDR
185 corrections. This includes tools like *Earth Trend Modeler* in *TerrSet* (Eastman, 2023) and
186 R packages such as *kendall* (McLeod, 2022), *trend* (Pohlert, 2023), or *Modifiedmk*
187 (Patakamuri and O'Brien N, 2021). The lack of implementation of this correction in such
188 widely used tools suggests a significant gap in controlling the false discovery rate within
189 remote sensing. This contrasts with software like *ArcGIS Pro* (ESRI, 2024), where FDR
190 control is integrated directly within the *Spatial Statistics* Toolbox, offering a more
191 comprehensive approach to managing false discoveries. Similarly, the R package
192 *GWmodel* for Geographically Weighted Models (Lu et al., 2023) includes functionality

193 to adjust p -values using FDR, enhancing the accuracy of spatial analyses by accounting
194 for multiple comparisons. Furthermore, it differs from other scientific fields, such as
195 medical imaging, where controlling FDR is more common and standardised practice
196 (Jenkinson et al., 2012).

197 The problems derived from multiple testing have only been occasionally raised in remote
198 sensing research. Clements et al. (2014) applied numerous testing procedures to detect
199 changes (not trends) in East African vegetation. Heumann (2015) highlighted the multiple
200 comparison problems in remote sensing and proposed solutions to address the issue of
201 multiple testing. He also noted that in a search across a wide range of disciplines in the
202 natural and physical sciences related to remote sensing of the Earth's surface using the
203 *Web of Knowledge* (WoS), only seven remote sensing papers cited the Benjamini &
204 Hochberg (1995) method.

205 The BH paper has been among the most influential in recent decades (Van Noorden et
206 al., 2014). The FDR control is widely used in many fields related to remote sensing, where
207 spatial signals or gridded data are crucial, such as meteorology and climatology (Ventura
208 et al., 2004; Wilks, 2006), GIS and spatial analysis (Caldas de Castro and Singer, 2006;
209 Rogerson, 2024), astronomy and astrophysics (Hopkins et al., 2002; Miller et al., 2001).
210 Therefore, the significant absence in remote sensing research is particularly striking. It is
211 worth emphasising that FDR has become a standard for controlling the inflation of false
212 positives in research areas and applications related to health and medical imaging
213 sciences, where error management is critical (Chalkidou et al., 2015; Genovese et al.,
214 2002; MacHado, 2007; Nguyen et al., 2014; Singh and Dan, 2006).

215 Miller et al. (2001) and Hopkins et al. (2002) also state that the FDR approach relies on
216 the mathematical analyses of the distribution of the p -values and takes advantage of their
217 properties to control false positives across the whole image. Additionally, it focuses on a
218 key scientifically relevant parameter: the fraction of false discoveries over the total
219 number of discoveries. On the contrary, fixed-threshold approaches handle p -values as
220 unrelated, ignoring their statistical distribution and properties.

221 In previous works (Gutiérrez-Hernández and García, 2024a, 2024b, 2025), we analysed
222 spatiotemporal trends at local ($n = 27,828$), regional ($n = 47,635$), and global ($n =$
223 $570,650$) scales using the Contextual Mann–Kendall test (Neeti and Eastman, 2011)
224 combined with FDR control. In all cases, adjusting p -values for multiplicity led to a
225 systematic reduction in the number of apparently significant pixels. This effect was
226 quantified using the Discovery Inflation Index (DII) — defined as the ratio of uncorrected
227 significant results to FDR-corrected discoveries— which ranged from minimal (1.01) to
228 substantial (1.42). As demonstrated by Miller et al. (2001), inflation of statistical
229 significance in image-wide analyses depends mainly on the distribution of p -values,
230 rather than solely on the number of tests —a pattern corroborated by our empirical results.
231 Crucially, when the issue of multiple testing is neglected, researchers may fall into
232 selective inference (Gutiérrez-Hernández and García, 2025b): interpreting significance
233 based exclusively on a fixed threshold (e.g., $\alpha = 0.05$), without considering the broader
234 context of simultaneous inferences. This may lead to overconfident or misleading
235 interpretations of statistical significance, particularly in large-scale multiple testing.

236 While our Scopus-based review was designed to be transparent and reproducible, it
237 presents several limitations. The search was constrained to the 2004–2023 period and

238 excluded our publications to preserve neutrality in remote sensing, despite their direct
239 relevance. The comparison with neuroimaging was intended as a heuristic contrast, not a
240 fully controlled cross-disciplinary analysis. It should be interpreted as illustrative of how
241 other imaging-based fields have normalised FDR practices, rather than as a formal
242 benchmark. Notably, Heumann (2015) had already drawn attention to the lack of multiple
243 testing correction and the systematic omission of FDR procedures in remote sensing,
244 highlighting the need for more rigorous inferential practices. Our contribution builds on
245 this concern by providing a structured quantitative review and practical guidance. The
246 FDR control presented here —both the classical Benjamini–Hochberg (BH) and the
247 adaptive Benjamini–Krieger–Yekutieli (BKY)— are valid under conditions of
248 independence and positive dependence, and this type of spatial correlation is pervasive in
249 remote sensing datasets. Further methodological details and practical implementation are
250 provided in Supplemental Materials I and II. Other FDR-based procedures can explicitly
251 accommodate such dependence (Benjamini and Heller, 2007) or through resampling-
252 based approaches (Yekutieli and Benjamini, 1999), preserving FDR control without
253 imposing overly restrictive assumptions. While these methods may offer advantages in
254 highly specific scenarios, the classical BH and adaptive BKY procedures used here
255 perform robustly and efficiently in most practical applications.

256 Beyond FDR control, statistical correction does not replace interpretative responsibility.
257 Researchers must still assess whether a significant result is also meaningful in the context
258 of their discipline, geographic setting, and research objectives. Significance alone does
259 not imply relevance. This highlights the importance of maintaining philosophical and
260 methodological rigour throughout the research process —from hypothesis formulation to
261 data analysis and interpretation.

262 5. Conclusion.

263 Our findings reveal a gap in current methodologies for controlling spurious findings in
264 remote sensing research. This suggests that many studies may have inflated statistically
265 significant results, potentially leading to misleading conclusions and poor decision-
266 making. We propose that FDR control should routinely accompany the presentation of
267 results when massive hypothesis testing is performed. Incorporating FDR adjustments
268 allows for direct comparison between controlled and uncontrolled approaches, helping to
269 evaluate their impact on study outcomes. Reporting the uncertainty associated with
270 significant results is fundamental to good scientific practice and does not diminish
271 researchers' ability to highlight their findings. Addressing this gap is crucial to improving
272 the reliability and reproducibility of remote sensing studies, ensuring that significant
273 findings are significant rather than statistical artefacts.

274 To facilitate this, we provide supplementary material (see *Supplementary Material I &*
275 *II*) with the foundations and the practical implementation of two alternative procedures
276 for FDR correction applied to raster-based datasets. Both methods operate on a single
277 input: a raster layer containing *p-values*. The first, the classical Benjamini-Hochberg
278 (BH) method, assumes that all null hypotheses are true; the second, the adaptive
279 Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli (BKY) procedure, estimates the proportion of true null
280 hypotheses. While the adaptive approach offers increased statistical power, both methods
281 ensure robust false discovery rate control.

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382

383

384 **Box 1**

385 *Features and advantages of FDR control over previous approaches (see text).*

- 386 1. **A priori control of a scientifically meaningful quantity:** the average (expected)
387 proportion of false discoveries over total discoveries, comparable across studies.
- 388 2. **Versatility:** It works on p -values and can be applied with any valid statistical test.
- 389 3. **Ease of use:** It provides a straightforward method to determine, from a set of p -values,
390 which null hypotheses to reject to control for FDR at the pre-specified level.
- 391 4. **Adaptive nature & Efficiency:** The outperformance of the FDR approach is related
392 to its adaptive nature, which allows it to retain a high fraction of the power of
393 uncorrected fixed criteria while substantially reducing the false rejection rate.
- 394 5. **Stability:** The FDR procedure can accommodate new data sets while maintaining rate
395 control in the expanded set.
- 396 6. **Threshold flexibility:** Unlike single-threshold approaches, you cannot know which
397 threshold per test to reject individual p -values; you must first look at the complete set
398 of p -values.
- 399 7. **Handling correlated errors:** FDR can handle positively correlated errors, i.e., errors
400 that tend to occur together due to positive correlation between tests performed
401 between neighbouring pixels. This property is critical when analysing images, where
402 patterns make positive dependencies the rule.

403 **Table 1.** Results of the searches performed in the scientific database Scopus, according
 404 to the criteria indicated in section 2.2. The search number in the first column corresponds
 405 to those listed above. In the Variable Search String column, [1] corresponds to the journal
 406 title search field, whereas [2] corresponds to the article title-abstract-keywords search
 407 field. BH REFS refers to citations of the Benjamini & Hochberg (1995) The seminal paper
 408 found in the documents was filtered according to the criteria in column 2.

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SEARCH	VARIABLE SEARCH STRING	TOTAL REFS	BH REFS	BH REFS (%)
1	[1] REMOTE AND SENSING	89802	25	0.03
2	[1] REMOTE AND SENSING [2] AND trend AND analysis	3397	5	0.15
3	[1] REMOTE AND SENSING [2] [Spatio-temporal OR spatiotemporal] AND Trend AND Analysis	829	2	0.24
4	[2] = AND trend AND analysis AND [mann-kendall OR mann AND kendall]	197	0	0.00
5	NEUROIMAG* [1]	29276	1778	6.07
6	fMRI [2]	55089	1601	2.91

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